

Influence of Part-Time Work on Academic Performance among College of Business and Accountancy Students at Our Lady of Fatima University – Valenzuela Campus

John Sherwin G. Capistrano^{1*}, Shiela Mae A. Sapa^{1,2}, Heart A. Mendoza^{1,3}, Liziel A. Pesimo^{1,4}, Ma. Lovely M. Alcantara^{1,5}, Andrea Lein A. Antonio^{1,6}, Geraldine A. Galigo^{1,7}, Niño T. Magat^{1,8}, Arsenia U. Gallardo^{1,9}, Jeffrey T. Tillo^{1,10}, Maria Cristina F. Meñez^{1,11}, Sheilla Marie D. Apostol^{1,12}

¹Our Lady of Fatima University

*sherwincap03@gmail.com, ²iyelxxx@gmail.com, ³kysheartmendoza@gmail.com,

⁴lizielpesimo@gmail.com, ⁵lovely.alcantara2004@gmail.com, ⁶leinareniego@gmail.com,

⁷geraldine.galigo8@gmail.com, ⁸ntmagat@fatima.edu.ph, ⁹augallardo@fatima.edu.ph, ¹⁰jtillo@fatima.edu.ph, ¹¹mfmenez@fatima.edu.ph, ¹²sdapostol@fatima.edu.ph

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the influence of part-time employment factors—specifically time management, work schedule, and weekly working hours—on the academic performance of College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) students at Our Lady of Fatima University – Valenzuela Campus. Utilizing a quantitative descriptive research design and purposive sampling, data were collected from 34 working students via a structured Likert-scale survey. The demographic profile revealed a female-dominated sample (64.7%) primarily composed of seniors and juniors working 11–20 hours per week in the service or retail industry. Results indicated that respondents possessed highly developed time management ($M = 4.15$) and work schedule management skills ($M = 4.16$). However,

inferential analysis using Spearman's rho and Kruskal-Wallis tests showed no statistically significant relationship between the investigated work factors and students' Grade Weighted Average (GWA). Anchored in the Conservation of Resources (COR) Theory, the findings suggest that students successfully utilize adaptive strategies and flexible arrangements to protect their academic resources and maintain stable performance despite employment demands. While employment did not inherently compromise grades, the study concludes that students may maintain performance through intensified effort, highlighting the need for institutional monitoring and targeted academic support programs to prevent long-term burnout.

Keywords: *Part-time employment, Academic performance, Time management, Work schedule, College of Business and Accountancy, Conservation of Resources Theory, Flexible learning, Grade Weighted Average, Working students, Student resilience*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the rising cost of tuition, school supplies, and daily living expenses has prompted many college students to engage in part-time employment for financial and personal reasons. This situation is particularly evident among College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) students at Our Lady of Fatima University (OLFU) – Valenzuela Campus, who often balance academic responsibilities with paid work while enrolled in flexible or hybrid learning arrangements. The shift to flexible learning, accelerated by the Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, has provided students with greater control over their schedules but has also raised concerns regarding academic workload, time management, and stress (Cruz, 2024).

Several studies have examined the relationship between part-time employment and students' academic performance, yet the findings remain inconsistent. Some research suggests that part-time work under flexible learning environments may be associated with improved time management and self-discipline among working students (Cruz, 2024). In contrast, other studies indicate that longer working hours may be related to reduced study time, lower class participation, and increased academic pressure, potentially influencing academic outcomes (Bestlink College of the Philippines – Bulacan, 2022). These mixed results suggest that the relationship between part-time employment and academic performance varies depending on factors such as working hours, work schedules, and learning modality.

Despite the growing number of working students, limited empirical evidence focuses specifically on CBA students enrolled at Our Lady of Fatima University (OLFU) – Valenzuela, particularly within flexible or hybrid learning arrangements. While previous studies have explored part-time employment among college students in general, there remains a research gap in understanding how working hours and work schedules are associated with the academic performance of College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) students within this specific institutional context. Addressing this gap is important, as College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) programs often involve demanding coursework that involve demanding coursework that requires substantial time commitment, which may pose challenges for students engaged in part-time employment.

This quantitative, descriptive study aims to examine the relationship between part-time employment and the academic performance of College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) students at Our Lady of Fatima University (OLFU) –Valenzuela. It describes a sample/population, the goal is to provide insight into the characteristics of the sample, Thomas, Darrin & Zubkov, Pavel. (2023).

Specifically, it seeks to determine how working hours and work schedules are associated with students' grade point averages and study habits under flexible learning arrangements. The findings of this study may provide valuable insights for educators and administrators in developing academic support strategies and policies that consider the needs of working students while promoting academic success.

Literature Review

The link between part-time work and students' academic performance has been extensively studied, yielding varied results. Some research points to positive effects on academic outcomes, while others highlight negative impacts. Kroupová, Havránek, and Irsova (2024) present meta-analytic evidence indicating that the average effect of part-time work on academic performance is generally minor but heavily influenced by context. Their study reveals that factors like the number of hours worked, job type, and students' socioeconomic status play a role in the overall impact. The research underscores the necessity of considering the context in which students are employed when assessing the relationship between part-time work and academic achievement.

Thies (2023) investigated the impact of work intensity on international students' academic performance, finding that moderate work hours, typically under 20 per week, can improve time management and provide career-related experience. However, when work hours surpass 25 per week,

there is a marked decline in academic performance, particularly in Grade Weighted Average (GWA) and course completion. This aligns with Davis (2023), who argued that while part-time work can enhance time management and life skills, excessive work hours lead to burnout, diminished academic focus, and poor academic outcomes. Therefore, it is essential to find a balance in work hours to ensure that employment does not interfere with academic responsibilities.

The type of job also affects the relationship between part-time work and academic performance. Kroupová et al. (2024) found that students working in jobs related to their field of study tend to perform better academically, as such work often complements their academic pursuits. Conversely, those in unrelated jobs tend to experience a more negative impact on their academic performance, possibly due to the mental and physical demands of jobs not aligned with their academic goals. This finding is consistent with Thies (2023), who noted that students in high-stress or physically demanding jobs are more likely to face academic challenges compared to peers in less demanding roles.

In the Philippine context, flexible learning provides students with more control over how they manage their time, but it can also create additional pressure for those who are working. Aton (2024) observed that working students in flexible learning environments often face challenges in balancing their job responsibilities with academic requirements. Ulanday (2024) further noted that these challenges may be reflected in students' Grade Weighted Average (GWA) and overall academic performance, showing how managing time is crucial for maintaining steady academic outcomes. The time management allows students to allocate sufficient hours for studying, completing assignments, attending classes, and fulfilling work responsibilities. By planning schedules carefully and monitoring how they use their time, working students are better able to balance school and employment demands while maintaining consistent academic performance.

Academic performance, often measured through Grade Point Average (GPA), remains a central concern for working students. Time management emerges as a critical mediator in this relationship. Studies show that students who develop effective scheduling and prioritization strategies can maintain or even improve their grades despite work commitments (Phan, 2024). Locally, Filipino students have adopted practical strategies such as task batching, fixed study windows, and negotiating work schedules to preserve academic performance (Pedroso, Aponte, & Juanico, 2023). These findings suggest that time management should be considered both as a control variable and a survey item in quantitative studies.

Being a working student has both positive and negative effects on academic performance. Students who work part-time developed essential skills such as adaptability, responsibility, and time management which contributed to maintaining a good academic result. They also express satisfaction with the knowledge they get while studying and working simultaneously. However, some respondents still had a neutral answer regarding class participation, attentiveness to their lectures, learning lessons, and going over modules, indicating that employment may occasionally divide their focus between work and study (Godio et al., 2021).

Contextual factors further shape this dynamic. During the Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic, Malaysian students working longer hours reported lower academic outcomes, while some adapted through online learning strategies (Mohd Shafie et al., 2020). In the Philippines, flexible learning arrangements and self-regulated learning have shown mixed associations with academic performance, depending on income, strand, and support systems (Flores Cruz, 2024). Similarly, Quezon City University (QCU) students working under 15 hours weekly maintained satisfactory Grade Point Averages (GPA), while those in fast-food or retail jobs with frequent absenteeism showed lower performance (QCU Lamp, 2023).

Student employment has become widespread globally, yet its impact on retention and academic success varies. In Europe, students working long hours—especially those without academic family backgrounds—are more likely to leave university early (Lessky & Unger, 2022). In the Philippines, students often work due to financial need, self-development, or the desire to integrate theory and practice. Effective time management and self-reflection help them navigate these dual roles (Abenoja et al., 2019).

Among Filipino business students, employment influences both academic outcomes and time management. While work-related strategies are often prioritized, academic-related time management tends to lag, suggesting a need for better organization and prioritization of academic tasks (Bangquiao et al., 2023). Prioritization, overcoming procrastination, and balancing socialization are key to optimizing productivity and achieving academic success (Calonia et al., 2023). These findings reinforce the importance of structuring time with precision to meet academic goals.

Work-hour thresholds are consistently linked to academic performance. Students working fewer than 15 hours weekly tend to maintain better grades and emotional stability, while those exceeding 20 hours face sleep deprivation and burnout (Dawar, 2025). Globally, excessive work hours reduce academic engagement and Grade Point Average (GPA) scores (Watanabe & Falci, 2020). In rigorous disciplines like nursing and business, working over 15 hours a week is linked to a notable drop in academic performance (Salamonson et al., 2023).

Gender also influences coping mechanisms. Female students with fewer work hours tend to exhibit stronger academic resilience, whereas male students working more hours experience increased stress and lower grades (Dawar, 2025). These results highlight the importance of considering both quantitative limits and qualitative experiences when evaluating the balance between work and study.

Time management plays a key role in how working students handle both school and job responsibilities, which can be reflected in their academic performance, including grades. Students who are able to organize their time effectively can allocate sufficient hours for studying, completing assignments, attending classes, and fulfilling work responsibilities. Good time management helps students maintain focus, avoid procrastination, and reduce stress, which supports consistent performance in their coursework. For students with part-time jobs, the ability to plan and prioritize tasks is particularly important to keep up with academic requirements (Zimmerman, 2023).

The relationship between time management and grades is influenced by how students structure their daily routines and balance competing demands. Students who plan their schedules carefully, set realistic deadlines, and monitor how they use their time are more likely to maintain steady academic performance. Conversely, students who struggle with organizing their tasks may find it harder to keep up with schoolwork, which can be reflected in lower grades. This highlights that the way working students manage their time is associated with differences in academic performance, without implying that time management alone determines grades (Cabello, 2022).

Theoretical Framework

Figure 1. *Conservation of Resources Theory as a Basis for Examining the Influence of Part-Time Employment on Academic Performance.*

Theoretical framework showing the method of researchers theorize humans experience and react to stress. It is based on the fundamental principle that humans have evolved to acquire and protect resources, (measured by Grade Weighted Average) of College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) students engaged in part-time employment, grounded in Conservation of Resources (COR) Theory (1989).

The framework integrates theoretical perspective to explain the influence of work-related factors on academic performance. Conservation Theory explains how individuals experience and respond to stress

by emphasizing the importance of resource management, which provides a basis for analyzing the academic performance of College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) students engaged in part-time employment.

This research is grounded in following of resources that explain how part-time employment affects the academic performance of college students, Hobfoll defines resources as the “objects, personal characteristics, conditions, or energies that are valued by the individual or that serve as a means for attainment of these objects, personal characteristics, conditions, or energies (Treadway et al., 2005).

This means that the resources are categorized into four types: (a) objects, (b) conditions, (c) personal characteristics, and (d) energies.

The first category of resources distinguished by Hobfoll, Madden et al. (2017) describes objects. Object resources are mainly direct resources and are valued because of some aspect of their physical nature or because of their acquiring secondary status value based on their rarity and expense (Madden et al., 2017). As an example, a home is an object resource that is valued for providing shelter, while a mansion is an object resource that may be valued for indicating status (Madden et al., 2017). As a second category of resources, Madden et al. (2017) speaks of conditions. Examples of condition resources are marriage or tenure, in the sense that ‘being married to someone’ or ‘being employed’ represent conditions. The third category of resources refers to personal characteristics. According to Madden et al. (2017), these are “resources to the extent that they generally aid stress resistance”, which suggests that they are primarily considered indirect resources. The fourth and final category of resources consists of energies. Examples of energy resources include time, money, and knowledge. These resources are largely considered indirect/secondary resources, which serve the purpose of facilitating the acquisition of other resources (Madden et al., 2017). For example, (Kim et al., 2016) argues that in the course of goal-directed behaviour, individuals draw on energy resources such as money and social credit and evaluate the efficiency of their behaviour based on the consumption of these resources (amongst other factors).

This theory provides a foundational framework for understanding how part-time employment influences academic performance. They guide the selection of variables and inform the interpretation of results within the context of working students in higher education.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 2. *Proposed Model on the Influence of Time Management, Work Schedule, and Work Hours on the Academic Performance of College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) Students.*

Conceptual framework showing the influence of time management, work schedule, and work hours per week on the Grade Weighted Average (GWA) of College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) students engaged in part-time employment.

The framework illustrates how the independent variables—time management, work schedule, and work hours per week—collectively influence the dependent variable, academic performance, measured through the Grade Weighted Average (GWA). This relationship is examined specifically among College of Business Administration (CBA) students at Our Lady of Fatima University (OLFU)–Valenzuela Campus who are engaged in part-time paid employment.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to examine the relationship between part-time employment factors and the academic performance of College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) students at Our Lady of Fatima University (OLFU)–Valenzuela under flexible learning arrangements.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. Age;
 - b. Sex;
 - c. Program;
 - d. Year Level;
 - e. Type of Work/Industry
 - f. Employment Period
2. Grade Weighted Average (GWA) of College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) students for the Second Semester, Academic Year 2024–2025
3. What are the factors affecting Part-time work in terms of:
 - a. Time management
 - b. Work schedule
 - c. Work hour per week
4. Is there a significant influence between time management and academic performance of College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) students at Our Lady of Fatima University– Valenzuela?
5. Is there a significant influence between working hours per week and the academic performance of College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) students?
6. Is there a significant influence between work schedule and the academic performance of College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) students?
7. Based on the results of the study, what academic support program or intervention may be proposed to assist College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) students at Our Lady of Fatima University–Valenzuela who are engaged in part-time employment?

METHODS

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative descriptive research design. The descriptive aspect was used to present statistical data on College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) students at Our Lady of Fatima University–Valenzuela who engage in part-time work, focusing on their work hours, work schedule and time management. The descriptive research may be conducted through observation, case studies, or survey research. Observation generally involves watching subjects, either in their natural setting or in a laboratory, and keeping careful records of what occurs. (EBSCO Research, 2023)

Specifically, this study focused on time management, weekly working hours, and work schedule to examine whether there are relationships with academic performance among student workers. Other work-related characteristics, such as employment type and duration of employment, were included only as descriptive contextual variables to provide a profile of the respondents and were not analyzed for relationships. This approach allows for deeper analysis, which is to identify patterns and the strength of relationships between variables without making claims about one variable causing changes in another.

Research Locale

The study will be conducted at Our Lady of Fatima University – Valenzuela Campus, located along MacArthur Highway, Valenzuela City. This campus is one of the main branches of the university and houses the College of Business and Accountancy (CBA), which offers programs in Accountancy, Accounting Information System, Marketing, and other business-related courses. The university offers a learning environment that encourages both academic growth and hands-on experience, making it appropriate for this research.

The study will focus on College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) students from first to fourth year who work part-time while studying. They were selected because their experiences in managing both academic and work responsibilities provide valuable insights into how part-time employment influences academic performance.

Population and Sampling

The population of this study consists of all registered College of Business Administration (CBA) students at Our Lady of Fatima University–Valenzuela Campus during the data collection period who are engaged in part-time paid employment. To ensure that the results are relevant and representative, only students meeting the following criteria were included: (1) formally enrolled in any CBA program, (2) actively engaged in paid employment, (3) employed for at least one month, and (4) have available academic grades that can be used for analysis. Students who are not working, only engage in unpaid volunteer services, or whose work is strictly curricular were excluded.

Given that the study specifically targets students with the qualification of being employed part-time, a purposive sampling method was employed. This non-probability technique was chosen because it allows the researchers to deliberately select participants who meet the inclusion criteria and are most relevant to the objectives of the study (Manalo, 2022). Whereas, it also entails that there is no pre-existing official database identifying working students within the college, a screening process was implemented to identify qualified respondents.

This approach ensures that the sample accurately represents the population of part-time working College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) students and allows for meaningful analysis of the relationships between work-related factors and academic performance.

Research Instrument

This study utilized a structured survey questionnaire as the primary research instrument for collecting quantitative data from Business and Accountancy (CBA) students at Our Lady of Fatima University–Valenzuela Campus who are engaged in part-time employment. The instrument was designed to examine the relationship between part-time work and academic performance, particularly in terms of General Weighted Average (GWA).

The questionnaire consists of two major sections. Section A focuses on the demographic profile of the respondents, including age, sex, academic program, year level, type of work or industry, and duration of employment. These variables provide contextual information for analyzing patterns and trends among working students. Section B consists of 36 Likert-scale statements related to Grade Weighted Average (GWA), time management, work schedule, and working hours per week. Responses are measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree.

The instrument was developed through a systematic and iterative process. An initial draft was prepared based on the study's conceptual framework and a review of related literature. This draft was reviewed by the research advisers and subsequently revised to improve clarity, consistency, and alignment with the study objectives. The revised questionnaire was then subjected to content validation by faculty members specializing in Social Studies and research methodology. Their feedback guided further refinement of selected items and response formats.

Ethical Considerations

This study adheres to established ethical principles and complies with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 to protect participants' rights, privacy, and welfare while ensuring research integrity. Participation is voluntary, and respondents may withdraw at any time without penalty. Only one survey response per participant will be accepted to maintain data quality. Informed consent will be obtained through a plain-language information sheet outlining the study's purpose, procedures, risks, and benefits. For online administration, consent is indicated by proceeding to the survey after reviewing the information, with an optional signature form available upon request.

Risks are minimal, though some questions may be perceived as personal. To mitigate discomfort, all items are optional, phrased carefully, and participants may skip questions. While no direct benefits are guaranteed, findings may indirectly inform university policies and support services for working students. Confidentiality and anonymity are prioritized; no student numbers, emails, or IP addresses will be collected. Data will be stored securely on an encrypted, password-protected university drive accessible only to the research team. Identifiers will be removed prior to analysis, and deidentified datasets will be retained for five years before secure deletion.

In accordance with the Data Privacy Act, identifiable or raw materials will be retained only as needed for verification or audit, up to 12 months after study closure unless otherwise required by the ethics committee. Deidentified datasets and supporting documentation will be retained for five years. After the retention period, electronic files will be securely deleted using institution-approved methods, and disposal actions will be logged and certified by the Principal Investigator. Results will be reported in aggregate, and any external sharing will require prior ethics approval, ensuring that all data handling practices uphold confidentiality, integrity, and lawful compliance.

Data Collection

The data gathering process began with securing approval from the appropriate authorities of Our Lady of Fatima University–Valenzuela Campus. After approval was granted, the researchers identified eligible respondents through an initial screening based on the established inclusion criteria. Only College of Business Administration (CBA) students who were currently enrolled, engaged in paid part-time employment for at least one month, and had an available General Weighted Average (GWA) were considered qualified to participate in the study.

Because the study specifically targeted students with the qualification of being employed part-time, a purposive sampling method was employed. This non-probability technique was chosen because it allowed the researchers to deliberately select participants who met the inclusion criteria and were most relevant to the objectives of the study (Manalo, 2022). The exact number of qualified students was not predetermined; instead, all students who satisfied the criteria during the screening process were invited to participate.

A structured survey questionnaire was then distributed primarily through online access via Google Forms. QR codes and survey links were shared on class group chats to facilitate easy access and encourage participation. Before completing the questionnaire, participants were provided with an informed consent form that described the study's purpose, emphasized voluntary participation, and guaranteed confidentiality and anonymity. The survey remained accessible for two weeks, allowing sufficient time for responses. After data collection ended, all responses were verified for completeness and prepared for statistical analysis. The

data gathered were used solely for academic purposes and treated in accordance with ethical standards for educational research.

Data Analysis

The collected data was tabulated and arranged for deriving frequencies and percentages, the results were re-arranged in simplified form for interpretation. Survey on the Impact of Part-Time Employment on the Academic Performance of College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) Students

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. *Sex of Respondents (N = 34)*

Category	n	%
Female	22	64.7
Male	12	35.3
Total	34	100.0

Note. Percentages are based on N = 34.

The overwhelming majority of the sample is represented by females (64.7%), and males by 35.3%. That is an indication that there are higher representations of women in the group of working College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) students surveyed, and it will influence the general patterns of time management and academic performance.

Table 2. *Program/Course of Respondents (N = 34)*

Program/Course	n	%
BSAIS	11	32.4
BSBA – Marketing Management	9	26.5
BSBA – Banking and Finance	8	23.5
BSA	5	14.7
BSOM	1	2.9
Total	34	100.0

Note. Percentages are based on N = 34.

The respondents will be selected in several College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) programs projected by BS in Accounting Information System (BSAIS) (32.4%), then BS in Business Administration (BSBA)-Marketing Management (26.5%), and BS in Business Administration (BSBA)-Banking and Finance (23.5%). Smaller shares are associated with BS in Accountancy (BSA) (14.7%) and BS in Operations Management (BSOM) (2.9%).

Table 3. *Year Level of Respondents (N = 34)*

Year Level	n	%
4th Year	15	44.1
3rd Year	12	35.3
2nd Year	6	17.6
1st Year	1	2.9
Total	34	100.0

Note. Percentages are based on N = 34.

The respondents are mostly in the upper years of study, 4th-year students and 3rd-year students are 44.1 and 35.3 percent. Students in second years constitute 17.6, with an exception of one in the 1st year (2.9).

Table 4. *Type of Work/Industry of Respondents (N = 34)*

Type of Work/Industry	n	%
Service/Retail	15	44.1
Freelance	10	29.4
BPO	6	17.6
Business owner	3	8.8
Total	34	100.0

Note. Percentages are based on N = 34.

The participation in work is focused on service-related jobs: The main activities of the respondents are Service/Retail 44.1 percent and then Freelance work 29.4 percent. Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) work has 17.6 and 8.8 indicate being an owner of a business.

Table 5. *Hours Worked per Week of Respondents (N = 34)*

Hours Worked per Week	n	%
11–20 Hours	18	52.9
1–10 Hours	7	20.6
31+ Hours	6	17.6
21–30 Hours	3	8.8
Total	34	100.0

Note. Percentages are based on N = 34.

Moderate part-time working (52.9) is the most widespread pattern of work arrangement as more than half of the respondents (52.9) work 11-20 hours a week. The other 20.6 percent unemployed work 1-10 hours, 17.6 percent heavy working 31+ hours; 8.8 percent working 21-30 hours.

Table 6. *Work Schedule Type of Respondents (N = 34)*

Work Schedule Type	n	%
Flexible	15	44.1
Shifting	10	29.4
Fixed	7	20.6
On-call	2	5.9
Total	34	100.0

Note. Percentages are based on N = 34.

Just under 50% of the respondents report the ability to have flexible schedules (44.1%) which means that most students want their work to be flexible to accommodate their classes. Shifting schedules also represent (29.4%), although fixed schedules take place 20.6% and on-call work (5.9).

Table 7. *Duration of Employment of Respondents (N = 34)*

Duration of Employment	n	%
> 1 year	22	64.7
7–12 months	12	35.3
Total	34	100.0

Note. Percentages are based on N = 34.

Most respondents have a working-time of over a year (64.7), with 35.3 having 7 -12 months of employment. This implies that most of the participants have accumulated work experience and not new jobs.

Table 8. *Time Management: Item Means, Standard Deviations, and Verbal Interpretation*

Mean	Verbal Interpretation
3.26 – 4.00	Highly Developed / Highly Agree
2.51 – 3.25	Developed / Agree
1.76 – 2.50	Slightly Developed / Disagree
1.00 – 1.75	Not Developed at All / Highly Disagree

Item	M	SD	VI	Rank
I plan my schedule to balance academic and work tasks.	4.32	0.68	Highly Developed / Highly Agree	1
I set specific study hours even while working.	4.24	0.61	Highly Developed / Highly Agree	2
I can complete my school requirements despite working.	4.15	0.78	Highly Developed / Highly Agree	3
I use my free time productively for school work.	4.15	0.66	Highly Developed / Highly Agree	3
I am able to maintain strong cognitive performance (e.g., focus, memory, problem-solving) in academics even with consecutive work shifts.	4.06	0.78	Highly Developed / Highly Agree	4
I am able to balance school and work without feeling overwhelmed.	4.00	0.85	Highly Developed / Highly Agree	5

Grand mean	4.15	0.52	Highly Developed / Highly Agree
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Note. The overall results indicate a highly developed level of time management and cognitive performance among working students ($M = 4.15$, $SD = 0.52$). Based on subsequent inferential analysis conducted at the .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was accepted.

Findings show a tendency to time management among working students, the results have a grand mean of 4.15 ($SD = 0.52$), which is perceived as agree. The most rated behaviors were determining a schedule to work and study ($M = 4.32$, $SD = 0.68$) and deciding when to study specifically ($M = 4.24$, $SD = 0.61$), both rated as strongly agree, which implies that they planned their time responsibly. Students also confirmed that they are able to fulfill demands and spend free time in a productive way (both $M = 4.15$). Reduced, but still favorable scores were observed in terms of sustaining the same cognitive performance with the shift in shifts ($M = 4.06$) and preventing overwhelm ($M = 4.00$) with an implication of manageable, yet existent strain.

The data utilized through Spearman rank correlation as it presented the responses of rank levels of agreement as it is appropriate to measure the strength and direction of the relationship between variables of the study.

Table 9. *Work Schedule: Item Means, Standard Deviations, and Verbal Interpretation*

Item	M	SD	VI	Rank
My work schedule is predictable enough to plan school tasks around.	4.32	0.59	Highly Developed / Highly Agree	1
I am able to maintain consistent class attendance despite my work schedule.	4.21	0.88	Highly Developed / Highly Agree	2
I can still focus during lectures even when working.	4.18	0.63	Highly Developed / Highly Agree	3
My work schedule rarely forces me to miss deadlines.	4.15	0.86	Highly Developed / Highly Agree	4
I feel alert and energized during classes even with work commitments.	4.09	0.87	Highly Developed / Highly Agree	5
I can manage sudden schedule changes without compromising my studies.	4.03	0.94	Highly Developed / Highly Agree	6
Grand mean	4.16	0.64	Highly Developed / Highly Agree	

Note. The results indicate a highly developed level of work schedule management among working students ($M = 4.16$, $SD = 0.64$). Based on subsequent inferential analyses conducted at the .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was accepted.

Results indicate overall positive assessments of work schedule compatibility with academic needs, which has a grand mean 4.16 ($SD = 0.64$), which can be construed as agree. The highest item presents a high confidence that schedules are predictable enough to plan school activities ($M = 4.32$) and therefore respondents are able to plan studying activities in relation to their work activities. There are also students who claimed that the attendance has been stable ($M = 4.21$) and the concentration during lectures has been excellent ($M = 4.18$), which shows that there are no overwhelming scheduling stressors. Nevertheless, less agreement was found when managing abrupt schedule adjustments ($M = 4.03$) and being refreshed at school ($M = 4.09$), which means that on the one hand, unpredictability and fatigue still represent minor issues, even in the face of overall flexibility.

Table 10. *Work Hours per Week: Item Means, Standard Deviations, and Verbal Interpretation*

Item	M	SD	VI	Rank
I can adjust my working hours when needed for school.	4.21	0.59	Agree	1
I can attend school activities without being affected by work hours.	3.88	0.84	Agree	2
My working hours allow me enough time to review for exams.	3.88	0.88	Agree	2
I sometimes prioritize work over school tasks.	3.82	0.83	Agree	3
My work hours reduce my study time.	3.82	0.83	Agree	3
Consecutive work shifts affect my academic performance.	3.79	0.84	Agree	4
Grand mean	3.90	0.49	Agree	

Note. The results indicate that respondents generally agreed that their work hours influence their academic responsibilities (M = 3.90, SD = 0.49). Based on subsequent inferential analyses conducted at the .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was accepted.

Results indicate overall positive assessments of work schedule compatibility with academic needs, which has a grand mean 4.16 (SD = 0.64), which can be construed as agree. The highest item presents a high confidence that schedules are predictable enough to plan school activities (M = 4.32) and therefore respondents are able to plan studying activities in relation to their work activities. There are also students who claimed that the attendance has been stable (M = 4.21) and the concentration during lectures has been excellent (M = 4.18), which shows that there are no overwhelming scheduling stressors. Nevertheless, less agreement was found when managing abrupt schedule adjustments (M = 4.03) and being refreshed at school (M = 4.09), which means that on the one hand, unpredictability and fatigue still represent minor issues, even in the face of overall flexibility.

Table 11. *Summary of Tests of Significant Relationships with Academic Performance (Grade Midpoint)*

Relationship	Test	Statistic	p	Strength	Decision
Time management & grades	Spearman ρ	0.034	0.849	Very weak	Not significant
Work schedule type & grades	Kruskal–Wallis H	1.856	0.603	—	Not significant
Hours worked/week & grades	Spearman ρ	-0.180	0.308	Very weak	Not significant
Work type/industry & grades	Kruskal–Wallis H	2.637	0.451	—	Not significant
Duration of employment & grades	Mann–Whitney U	96.5	0.177	—	Not significant

All tests were evaluated at $\alpha = .05$. Spearman ρ strength guide: $|\rho| < .20$ very weak, $.20-.39$ weak, $.40-.59$ moderate, $.60-.79$ strong, $\geq .80$ very strong.

The findings suggest that there are no statistically significant links between academic performance (midpoint grade) and the measured factors regarding employment-related variables at 0.05. The monotonic correlation between time management and grades (0.034 = 0.849) was close to zero, suggesting that these variables do not have a monotonic relationship in this sample. The hours per week were also weakly and negatively correlated with the grades ($r = -0.180$, $p = 0.308$), which indicates that more work hours did not certainly mean lower grades. The significant differences between the groups were also not significant in the work schedule type (H = 1.856, $p = .603$), work type/industry (H = 2.637, $p = .451$), and duration of employment (U = 96.5, $p = .177$). In general, the grades do not seem to be affected by the work changes in the respondents.

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to determine whether time management, work schedule, and hours worked per week influence the academic performance of College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) students at Our Lady of Fatima University – Valenzuela who are engaged in part-time employment. The findings indicated that these part-time employment factors did not exert a statistically significant influence on students' GWA, suggesting that, within this sample, part-time work did not meaningfully affect academic performance.

The findings showed that the respondents reported highly developed time management skills, with a grand mean of 4.15, indicating that they generally agreed that they planned their schedules, set specific study hours, and used their free time productively for academic tasks. At the same time, the Spearman rank correlation between time management and academic performance was very weak and not significant, which means that higher self-reported time management did not translate into a clear pattern of higher or lower grades. This suggests that most of the respondents, regardless of small differences in their time management scores, were already functioning at a relatively competent level, enough to maintain their academic performance while working.

These results can be understood in light of literature emphasizing that time management is a supporting factor rather than a sole determinant of grades. Prior studies have noted that students who plan their schedules, set priorities, and monitor their tasks are more capable of sustaining performance despite external demands, but they also highlight that other variables such as motivation, support systems, and course difficulty can shape outcomes. In this study, the consistently high time management scores may have reduced variability, making it harder to detect a statistical link with academic performance, even though effective time use likely contributed to students' ability to cope with both work and school.

The respondents also expressed generally positive perceptions of their work schedules, with a grand mean of 4.16, indicating that most of them found their schedules predictable enough to plan school tasks around, and they were able to maintain class attendance and concentration during lectures. Despite this, statistical tests showed no significant differences in academic performance across work schedule types (flexible, shifting, fixed, on-call), suggesting that schedule type alone did not distinguish high- and low-performing students in this group. One possible explanation is that many respondents had schedules that were already adjusted to their academic responsibilities, which minimized direct conflicts between work and school.

In terms of work hours per week, more than half of the respondents reported working 11–20 hours, which can be considered a moderate level of part-time employment. The correlation between hours worked and GWA was weakly negative and not significant, indicating that increases in weekly work hours were not clearly associated with lower grades. This pattern differs from studies that reported strong negative effects when students worked long hours, but it aligns with research suggesting that moderate work hours, when combined with good self-regulation, may not necessarily damage academic performance. The concentration of respondents in the 11–20-hour range, along with their high time management scores, may have buffered them from the academic risks often linked with heavier workloads.

The results may be interpreted using Conservation of Resources (COR) Theory, which posits that individuals strive to acquire, protect, and manage valuable resources such as time, energy, and knowledge. In this study, working CBA students appeared to manage their key resources in a way that prevented serious academic loss. Their ability to plan schedules, maintain attendance, and adjust work hours when needed suggests that they were actively preserving their academic resources despite the additional demands of part-time employment. The absence of significant negative effects on academic performance implies that these students were able to prevent major resource depletion in the academic domain, which is consistent with Conservation of Resources (COR) Theory's emphasis on strategic resource management in stressful contexts.

The finding that part-time work did not significantly influence GWA has important implications for students, faculty, and administrators. For students, the results indicate that it is possible to combine work

and study successfully when work hours are manageable and time management skills are well developed. For faculty and advisers, the evidence supports the value of reinforcing planning, scheduling, and self-regulation strategies, rather than discouraging employment outright. For college and university, the study suggests that policies and programs that support flexible scheduling, provide guidance for working students, and acknowledge their dual roles can help sustain academic performance even when students are employed. Despite these contributions, the study has several limitations. The sample size was relatively small and drawn through purposive sampling, which limits the generalizability of the findings to all CBA students or to other programs and campuses. The measures of time management, work schedule, and work hours were also self-reported, which may be influenced by social desirability or recall bias. In addition, the design was cross-sectional, capturing only one point in time and not allowing for conclusions about changes in academic performance before and after employment.

CONCLUSIONS

This study examined the influence of time management, work schedule, and hours worked per week on the academic performance of College of Business and Accountancy students engaged in part-time employment. The findings indicate that these work-related factors did not significantly influence students' academic performance. The proposed relationships between part-time work variables and grade outcomes were not supported.

Despite balancing employment and academic responsibilities, the respondents were able to sustain stable academic performance. The findings suggest that working students in this context have developed adaptive strategies that allow them to manage competing demands effectively. Strong self-regulation practices and the presence of flexible work arrangements appear to function as protective factors that buffer potential academic disruption.

Anchored in Conservation of Resources Theory, the results imply that students were able to preserve essential academic resources such as time, focus, and cognitive energy despite employment obligations. Rather than experiencing measurable academic decline, they demonstrated resilience and strategic resource allocation.

However, the absence of statistical significance should not be interpreted as the absence of impact. Academic performance, measured solely through grades, may not fully capture subtle forms of strain such as fatigue, reduced rest, compressed study time, or increased pressure during peak academic periods. It is possible that students maintain performance through intensified effort, which may not be sustainable in the long term.

Therefore, the study concludes that part-time employment does not inherently compromise academic performance among CBA students under flexible learning conditions. Nonetheless, the relationship appears to be conditional and potentially masked by strong coping mechanisms, indicating the need for continued institutional awareness and support.

Recommendations

While no significant relationship was found between part-time work factors and academic performance, the study revealed a critical gap: academic grades alone may not fully reflect the lived experience of working students. The findings suggest that students may be maintaining performance through compensatory effort rather than experiencing zero academic strain. This highlights the need for proactive monitoring and structured support mechanisms beyond grade evaluation.

For University Management and CBA Faculty

1. Institutionalize a Working Student Monitoring Framework

Develop a structured advising protocol specifically for students engaged in part-time employment. This may include periodic academic consultations that assess workload balance, study time sustainability, and perceived academic pressure. Early detection systems can prevent potential long-term academic decline.

2. Integrate Preventive Academic Support Programs

Offer targeted workshops on advanced time management, energy management, and burnout prevention. Since students rely heavily on self-regulation to sustain performance, reinforcing these skills ensures long-term sustainability rather than short-term compensation.

3. Promote Academic Flexibility with Structured Accountability

Faculty may implement transparent scheduling, recorded lectures, and advance academic calendars to assist working students in planning effectively. Structured flexibility reduces uncertainty and minimizes last-minute academic compression.

For CBA Students

Working students are encouraged to critically assess not only their grades but also their overall well-being. Sustained academic performance should not come at the expense of sleep, health, or long-term burnout. Proactive consultation with academic advisers when experiencing workload imbalance is strongly recommended.

For Future Researchers

Future studies should explore longitudinal outcomes to determine whether sustained part-time employment produces cumulative academic or psychological effects over time. Expanding the research to include variables such as stress levels, sleep quality, and academic motivation may provide a more comprehensive understanding of the work–study dynamic. Mixed-method approaches may also uncover hidden dimensions of strain not reflected in quantitative grade measures.

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